

Table 1: Activity table of the SEPCAM PDD

Activity	Sub-activity	Description
Establish goal	Determine goal	Upper management of the orchestrator defines a GOAL that it wants to pursue for a certain time period that the orchestrator can set itself. This process is supported by using the GOAL-ROLE-CHARACTERISTIC FRAMEWORK.
Select partners	Select preferred characteristics	Based on the defined GOAL and recommended CHARACTERISTICS from the GOAL-ROLE-CHARACTERISTIC FRAMEWORK the partner management of the orchestrator creates a LIST OF CHOSEN CHARACTERISTICS that support reaching the defined GOAL.
	Select partner roles	Based on the LIST OF CHOSEN CHARACTERISTICS and with the support of the GOAL-ROLE-CHARACTERISTIC FRAMEWORK, the partner management of the orchestrator creates a LIST OF CHOSEN PARTNER ROLES that complements the CHARACTERISTICS.
	Label partners with roles	While a shortlist of partners is being defined, the partner management of the orchestrator labels these PARTNERS with one or multiple PARTNER ROLES, resulting in a LIST OF LABELED PARTNERS that the orchestrator can use for faster identification of suitable PARTNERS in a following iteration of this process.
	Select partners	When the LIST OF CHOSEN PARTNER ROLES has been created, the partner management of the orchestrator searches its network of PARTNERS that have been identified as the corresponding PARTNER ROLES. This results in a concrete LIST OF CHOSEN PARTNERS in which the orchestrator can then allocate resources to, to achieve its defined GOAL.
Investment in chosen partners	Allocate resources	When the LIST OF CHOSEN PARTNERS is established, the partner management of the orchestrator then allocates resources to them through the means of an INVESTMENT SCHEME.
	Monitor investment	The management of the orchestrator monitors its investments in the PARTNERS through an INVESTMENT REPORT to evaluate if this allocation of resources has helped in achieving the defined GOAL.

Table 2: Concept table of the SEPCAM PDD.

Concept	Description
LIST OF LABELED PARTNERS	An administrative overview of the PARTNERS an orchestrator already has, where the PARTNERS are labeled with one or more PARTNER ROLES that they can perform [?, ?].
PARTNER	A PARTNER is an organization that extends the characteristics of the orchestrator. Together with the orchestrator, the PARTNERS co-create value within the software ecosystem by offering additional functionality [?, ?].
GOAL	A desired result, accompanied with recommended CHARACTERISTICS to meet said result [?].
GOAL-ROLE-CHARACTERISTIC FRAMEWORK	The framework as proposed in section ??.
LIST OF CHOSEN CHARACTERISTICS	A collection of CHARACTERISTICS as chosen by the orchestrator that should complement the desired GOAL [?].
CHARACTERISTIC	A feature, quality or capability belonging to a PARTNER, PARTNER ROLE or GOAL, serving to identify them [?, ?, ?].
LIST OF CHOSEN PARTNER ROLES	A collection of PARTNER ROLES that are most suitable with the LIST OF CHOSEN CHARACTERISTICS [?, ?, ?, ?, ?].
PARTNER ROLE	A specialization of PARTNERS which deliver a specific type of value [?].
LIST OF CHOSEN PARTNERS	A collection of PARTNERS that fit the LIST OF CHOSEN PARTNER ROLES [?, ?].
INVESTMENT SCHEME	A plan on how to actually allocate resources to the chosen PARTNERS [?].
INVESTMENT REPORT	A report with the results of allocating the resources to the selected PARTNERS, aiming to uncover if the defined GOAL has been met [?].